

the standing rice crop at two seeding rates (normal and 50% higher than normal) with and without fertilizer. Fertilizer was broadcast 3 d before sowing the intercrop. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Rice yield was 3.8 t/ha. Yields of gram, linseed, and lentil ranged from 0.12 to 0.17, 0.45 to 0.68, and 0.16 to 0.29 t/ha, respectively. (Lower yields of gram and linseed were due to a winter drought.)

Rice - linseed produced significantly higher rice equivalency yield than rice - gram and rice - lentil (see table). Linseed with fertilizer yielded significantly higher than other crops. The interaction between crops and seeding rates was not significant. ■

Productivity of rice-based intercropping systems in Pusa, Bihar, India, 1988-89.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Rice	Intercrop	Rice yield Equivalence
Rice alone	3.7	-	3.7
Rice + gram, normal seeding rate. no fertilizer (S ₁ F ₁)	3.7	0.1	4.1
Rice + gram, normal seeding rate. fertilized ^a (S ₁ F ₂)	3.7	0.2	4.2
Rice + gram + 150% seeding. no fertilizer (S ₂ F ₁)	3.7	0.1	4.1
Rice + gram + 150% seeding, fertilized (S ₂ F ₂)	3.8	0.2	4.2
Rice + linseed + S ₁ F ₁	3.7	0.4	4.5
Rice + linseed + S ₁ F ₂	3.7	0.6	4.9
Rice + linseed + S ₂ F ₁	3.7	0.6	4.8
Rice + linseed + S ₂ F ₂	3.8	0.7	5.1
Rice + lentil + S ₁ F ₁	3.7	0.2	4.3
Rice + lentil + S ₁ F ₂	3.7	0.2	4.2
Rice + lentil + S ₂ F ₁	3.6	0.2	4.2
Rice + lentil + S ₂ F ₂	3.7	0.3	4.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	0.1	0.4

^a20 kg N + 18 kg P/ha for gram and lentil, 30 kg N + 9 kg P/ha for linseed.

Production potential and economics of upland rice + pigeonpea

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Upland rice + pigeonpea is the widely adopted mixed cropping system in Keonjhar. But grazing by stray cattle after rice harvest reduces pigeonpea yields. Pigeonpea remains in the field 2 mo longer, and farmers lose interest in protecting a thinly populated crop that may not give an adequate return. Recommended seeding rates for single crop rice and pigeonpea are 100 and 20 kg/ha, respectively.

We evaluated proportions of rice and pigeonpea during 1985-87 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Experimental crop schedules are given in the table.

Soil of the experimental site was sandy with pH 5.7, low available N (242 kg/ha) and P (8.0 kg/ha), and medium available K (97.0 kg/ha).

Rice cultivar Shankar (85 d duration) and pigeonpea UPAS 120 (145 d) were sown 21 Jun 1985, 24 Jun 1986, and 27 Jun 1987. Fertilizer was 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha for rice and 20-17.4-0 kg NPK/ha for pigeonpea.

Line sowing 2 rows of pigeonpea 50 cm apart after each 10 rows of rice 15 cm apart gave the highest return. ■

Yield and economics of rice + pigeonpea cropping system under different sowing methods and mixing proportions.^a Orissa, India, 1985-87.

Treatment		Yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Profit (\$/ha)
Sowing	Proportion			
Rice and pigeonpea mixed and broadcast	Rice 60% + pigeonpea 40%	1.2 1.2	506.44	342.81
	Rice 70% + pigeonpea 30%	1.5 1.0	463.38	297.38
	Rice 80% + pigeonpea 20%	1.6 0.9	444.88	276.56
	Rice 60% (1.5 m broadcast sown) + pigeonpea 40% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.3 1.4	565.81	399.75
Rice broadcast and pigeonpea line dibbled	Rice 70% (3.0 m broadcast sown) + pigeonpea 30% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.6 1.2	539.63	371.50
	Rice 80% (4.5 m broadcast sown) + pigeonpea 20% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.9 1.0	494.75	323.94
	Rice 60% (10 rows 15 cm apart) + pigeonpea 40% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.5 1.5	626.44	458.44
Rice and pigeonpea line sown	Rice 70% (20 rows 15 cm apart) + pigeonpea 30% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.6 1.3	599.31	418.69
	Rice 80% (30 rows 15 cm apart) + pigeonpea 20% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	2.1 1.1	563.00	391.63

^aAv of 2 yr.